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Solution of Fractional Derivative Homogeneous and Non-Homogeneous Parabolic Problems using the Fourier Method

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Abstract

In this paper, the solutions of homogeneous and non-homogeneous parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions are investigated using the Fourier method. In the solution process, the Sturm–Liouville equation is solved under periodic boundary conditions to determine the eigenvalues and corresponding eigenfunctions. Caputo fractional derivatives are employed, and the analytical solutions involve the Gamma and Beta functions, while the fractional-order solutions are expressed in terms of the Mittag–Leffler function. The results demonstrate that the Fourier method provides an effective analytical framework for solving fractional derivative semilinear pseudo-parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions.

Keywords: Fourier method, fractional derivative, periodic boundary conditions.

1. Introduction

Fractional differential equations are equations in which derivatives and integrals are not limited to integer orders but can also take real or complex values [1–10]. The origins of this field date back to ancient times, and the concept of fractional derivatives has long attracted the attention of mathematicians. Many prominent mathematicians have contributed to its development. Early studies were conducted by Leibniz and L'Hôpital (1695), Bernoulli (1697), Euler (1730), and Lagrange (1772). In the following years, numerous researchers such as Laplace (1812), Fourier (1822), Abel (1823), Liouville (1832), Riemann (1847), Grünwald (1867), Letnikov (1868), Hadamard (1892), Heaviside (1892), Weyl (1917), Zygmund (1945), J. L. Lions (1959), and Liverman (1964) further advanced the theory of fractional derivatives and integrals.

Fractional-order partial differential equations (PDEs) are used in many branches of science, including applied mathematics, physics, chemistry, and engineering. They have become a powerful mathematical tool for modeling complex processes and systems in these disciplines. These equations can provide more realistic models in cases where classical derivatives are insufficient. Fractional derivatives are history-dependent because they take into account not only the current state but also past

events. They reflect effects accumulated over time, making them particularly suitable for systems with memory. These properties have led to increasing interest in fractional derivatives in recent years.

Various definitions have been proposed for fractional derivatives. The Caputo and Riemann–Liouville definitions, which include integral-based expressions involving the Gamma function, are particularly prominent. Among these definitions, the Caputo derivative has become one of the most widely used in the literature due to its advantages. Because it allows initial conditions to be defined in the classical sense, the Caputo derivative yields more meaningful and applicable solutions when modeling physical processes. In this context, models incorporating the Caputo derivative produce results that are more consistent, applicable, and physically realistic compared to other fractional derivative definitions. Numerous studies supporting this view can be found in the literature [11–27].

2. General Information

2.1 The Gamma Function (Γ)

The gamma function is a special function used in fractional-order integral and derivative calculations.

Definition 2.1 The first definition was given by Gauss:

$$\Gamma(z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!n^z}{z(z+1)(z+2)\dots(z+n)}, \operatorname{Re}(z) > 0. \quad (1)$$

With this limit definition, Gamma (Γ) can be calculated for all values of z except for zero and negative integers [28].

Definition 2.2 The gamma function was also defined by Leonhard Euler in 1729, based on an integral transform. Euler's definition was developed to generalize the factorial of natural numbers. The definition commonly used today is:

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{z-1} dt, \operatorname{Re}z > 0. \quad (2)$$

With this definition, the gamma function can be calculated for all values of z [28].

Eq. (2) is valid for integer values of n . Since

$$n! = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^n dt$$

the gamma function is also referred to as the factorial function.

Some important properties of the gamma function include:

$$1) \Gamma(1) = 1$$

Here, if we use the limit definition made by Gauss,

$$\Gamma(1) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!n}{1.2.3\dots n(n+1)} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!n}{(n+1)n!} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n}{n+1} = 1.$$

$$2) \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi} \quad [28].$$

$$3) \Gamma(z + 1) = z \cdot \Gamma(z), z \in \mathbb{Z}$$

$$\Gamma(2) = \Gamma(1) = 1!$$

$$\Gamma(3) = 2\Gamma(2) = 2!$$

$$\Gamma(4) = 3\Gamma(3) = 3!$$

$$\Gamma(n + 1) = n \cdot \Gamma(n) = n \cdot (n - 1)! = n!$$

2.2 The Beta Function

The Gamma function, defined by Euler, forms the basis of many special functions. One of these is the Beta function. The Beta function is directly related to the Gamma function and is often used to simplify certain combinations of Gamma functions. It is also called the Euler integral of the first kind and is defined as follows:

$$B(z, \omega) = \int_0^1 \tau^{z-1} (1 - \tau)^{\omega-1} d\tau, \operatorname{Re}(z) > 0, \operatorname{Re}(\omega) > 0 \quad (3)$$

The Beta function can also be expressed in terms of the Gamma function as

$$B(z, \omega) = \frac{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(\omega)}{\Gamma(z + \omega)}$$

and it satisfies the symmetry property [28]

$$B(z, \omega) = B(\omega, z).$$

2.3 Mittag-Leffler Function (E)

Fractional differential equations are generally much more complex to solve than classical equations. A special function frequently used in the solution of such equations is the Mittag-Leffler function, named after Magnus Gustaf (Gösta) Mittag-Leffler. This function is a generalization of the exponential function for fractional differential equations and is particularly important in expressing solutions to initial value problems

$$E_{\alpha, \beta}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (4)$$

When $\beta=1$ it is called a single parameter Mittag-Leffler function. It is shown as

$$E_{\alpha}(z) = E_{\alpha, 1}(z),$$

$$E_{\alpha}(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha k)}$$

single parameter Mittag-Leffler function

$$E_{\alpha, \beta}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}, \alpha > 0$$

Two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function. When $\alpha=1, \beta=1$ is accepted, it reduces to the classical exponential function e^z . Therefore, Mittag-Leffler functions assume the role of the exponential function in fractional differential equations.

This series converges for all values of z when α, β are real and positive.

$$E_{\alpha,\alpha}(0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)},$$

$$E_{1,1}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k!} = e^z,$$

$$E_{1,2}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+2)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(k+1)!} = \frac{1}{z} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{e^z - 1}{z},$$

$$E_{1,3}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+3)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(k+2)!} = \frac{1}{z} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{k+2}}{(k+2)!} = \frac{e^z - 1 - z}{z^2},$$

$$E_{2,1}(z^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k}}{\Gamma(2k+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k+1}}{(2k)!} = \cosh(z),$$

$$E_{2,2}(z^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k}}{\Gamma(2k+2)} = \frac{1}{z} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} = \frac{\sinh(z)}{z}$$

Mittag–Leffler is a special expansion of the function [28].

2.4 Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative

Let f be a continuous and integrable function on the interval (a,t) , the Reiman-Liouville fractional derivative of f of order α for $t > a$ such that $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n - 1 \leq \alpha < n$ R-L Fractional derivative

$${}^R D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_a^t (t-\tau)^{n-\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (5)$$

2.5 Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral

$${}^R D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (6)$$

2.6 Caputo Fractional Derivative

The Caputo fractional derivative of order α is defined as:

$$D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^t \frac{f^{(n)}(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\alpha+1-n}} d\tau, \quad n - 1 < \alpha < n \quad (7)$$

The Caputo derivative can be considered a counterpart to the Riemann–Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative. The main difference between the R-L derivative and the Caputo derivative is the order in which the derivatives are taken: in the R-L derivative, the fractional derivative is applied first, followed by the integer-order derivative; in the Caputo derivative, the integer-order derivative is taken first, followed by the fractional derivative.

The Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative is not always suitable for applied problems because the initial conditions are tied to fractional integral limits, which cannot be directly interpreted in a classical sense.

The derivative of the constant in the R-L derivative is

$${}^R D_t^\alpha(c) = \frac{c \cdot t^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)}.$$

The derivative of the constant in the Caputo derivative is zero [28].

2.7 Fourier Series

$$f(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx) \quad (8)$$

The function series $f(x)$ with a period of 2π is called a Fourier Series. The coefficients a_0, a_n and b_n are called the Fourier coefficients. There are certain properties that a function must possess to be expanded into a Fourier series. The Fourier series must be uniformly convergent [30].

Definition 2.3 (Piecewise Continuity). A function is called a piecewise continuous function if it is continuous at all points except a finite number of points in the interval $[a, b]$ where it is defined [30].

Theorem 2.1 (Dirichlet's Theorem). If $f(x)$ and its derivatives are piecewise continuous on the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, then the Fourier series of $f(x)$ satisfies the following properties [30]:

1. At continuous points, the Fourier series converges to $f(x)$.
2. At discontinuity points, it converges to the average of the right and left limits:

$$\frac{f(x^+) + f(x^-)}{2}.$$

3. At the extreme points, it is equal to the average value of the right and left limits:

$$\frac{f(-\pi^+) + f(\pi^-)}{2}.$$

To find the Fourier coefficient a_0 over the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, integrate both sides of Eq. (8) with respect to x from $-\pi$ to π :

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} dx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx dx + b_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx dx).$$

Since for all $n \geq 1$:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx dx = 0.$$

all terms in the summation vanish. This leaves:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} dx = a_0 \pi.$$

Hence, the coefficient a_0 is:

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx. \quad (9)$$

To find the Fourier coefficient a_n , multiply both sides of Eq. (8) by $\cos(kx)$ and integrate over the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos kx dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} \cos kx dx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \cos kx dx + b_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \cos kx dx),$$

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \cos kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \cos kx dx = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq n \\ \pi, & k = n. \end{cases}$$

Finally, the Fourier coefficient a_n is given by:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx. \quad (10)$$

To find the Fourier coefficient b_n , multiply both sides of Eq. (8) by $\sin(kx)$ and integrate over the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin kx dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} \sin kx dx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \sin kx dx + b_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \sin kx dx),$$

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \sin kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \sin kx dx = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq n \\ \pi, & k = n. \end{cases}$$

Finally, the Fourier coefficient b_n is given by:

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx. \quad (11)$$

The coefficients given in Eqs. (9), (10), and (11) are called the Fourier series coefficients of Eq. (8) [30].

2.8 Sturm-Liouville Problem

The Sturm-Liouville equation is a second-order real linear differential equation. All its coefficients are continuous on the closed and finite interval $[a, b]$, and the derivative of $p(x)$ is also continuous.

If a function y is continuously differentiable on the interval (a, b) and satisfies Eq. (12) at every point, then y is a solution of this equation.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(p(x) \frac{dy}{dx} \right) + q(x)y = \lambda r(x)y, \quad (x) > 0, r(x) \geq 0. \quad (12)$$

The functions $p(x), q(x), r(x)$ are continuous in the interval $[a, b]$. Furthermore, the following boundary conditions are given.

$$a_1 y(a) + a_2 p(a) y'(a) = 0,$$

$$b_1 y(b) + b_2 p(b) y'(b) = 0. \quad (13)$$

The conditions $a_1^2 + a_2^2 \neq 0$ and $b_1^2 + b_2^2 \neq 0$ are met. The problem defined by Eqs. (12) and (13) is called a Sturm-Liouville problem. The nonzero solutions of this problem are called eigenvalues (λ), and the functions corresponding to these eigenvalues are called eigenfunctions [31].

2.9 Boundary Conditions

Consider the boundary conditions:

$$y(a) = y(b), y'(a) = y'(b)$$

If the Sturm-Liouville problem is defined with these conditions, it is called a periodic boundary condition Sturm-Liouville problem [31].

Let us solve the Sturm-Liouville problem under periodic boundary conditions and determine its eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. Consider the differential equation:

$$x'' + \lambda x = 0, x(0) = x(l), x'(0) = x'(l). \quad (14)$$

Problem (14) is a second-order differential equation with constant coefficients. To solve it, we first find the eigenvalues λ from the characteristic equation.

We will examine the three possible cases for the eigenvalue λ : when $\lambda < 0$, $\lambda = 0$, and $\lambda > 0$.

i) $\lambda < 0, \lambda = -m^2$.

$$k^2 + \lambda = 0, k^2 = m^2, \quad k = \mp m,$$

$$X(x) = Ae^{mx} + Be^{-mx} \quad (15)$$

Eq. (15) is the eigenfunction. When boundary conditions are applied to find the coefficients in the eigenfunction, $A = 0, B = 0$ is found. $X = 0$ is the obvious solution.

ii) $\lambda=0$,

$$X'' = 0, \quad X' = a_0 \quad X = a_0x + b_0.$$

When the boundary conditions are applied to the eigenfunction, we find $a_0 = 0, b_0 = 0$. $X = 0$ is the obvious solution.

iii) $\lambda > 0, \lambda = m^2$,

$$k^2 + \lambda = 0, \quad k^2 = -m^2, \quad k = \mp mi$$

$$X(x) = A_n \cos mx + B_n \sin mx.$$

The derivative of the eigenfunction is given by:

$$X'(x) = -mA_n \sin mx + mB_n \cos mx.$$

Periodic boundary conditions, as given in Eq. (14), are applied, we obtain

$$A_n = A_n \cos m\pi + B_n \sin m\pi,$$

$$B_n = -A_n \sin m\pi + B_n \cos m\pi,$$

$$A_n(1 - \cos m\pi) - B_n \sin m\pi = 0,$$

$$A_n \sin m\pi + B_n(1 - \cos m\pi) = 0.$$

For the solution of the system to be linearly independent, the coefficient determinant A_n, B_n must be zero.

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 - \cos m\pi & -\sin m\pi \\ \sin m\pi & 1 - \cos m\pi \end{vmatrix} = 0.$$

$$(1 - \cos m\pi)^2 + (\sin m\pi)^2 = 0,$$

$$1 - 2\cos m\pi + \cos^2 m\pi + \sin^2 m\pi = 0,$$

$$\cos m\pi = 1, m\pi = 2k\pi, m = 2k.$$

The eigenvalues are:

$$\lambda_n = (2k)^2.$$

The corresponding eigenfunctions are:

$$X = A_n \cos 2kx + B_n \sin 2kx.$$

That is, the two linearly independent functions corresponding to this eigenvalue are:

$$\lambda_k = \cos 2kx,$$

$$\lambda_k = \sin 2kx.$$

3. Fourier Method for Fractional Differential Parabolic Equation

3.1 Solution of Fractional Differential Homogeneous Parabolic Equation by Fourier Method

$$D_t^\alpha(U(x, t)) = U_{xx}, \quad x > 0, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (16)$$

$$U(0, t) = U(\pi, t), \quad U_x(0, t) = U_x(\pi, t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (17)$$

$$U(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq \pi. \quad (18)$$

The solution to the problem in the equation can be written as follows using Sturm-Liouville. The solution depends on the variables x and t . Therefore;

$$U(x, t; \alpha) = X(x)T(t; \alpha), \quad (19)$$

$$U_{xx} = X''T(t, \alpha),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U(x, t; \alpha)) = XD_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha)),$$

$$XD_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha)) = X''T(t; \alpha),$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha))}{T(t; \alpha)} = \frac{X''}{X} = -\lambda.$$

When the boundary conditions given in (17) are applied to the last equation, the following Sturm-Liouville problem is obtained.

$$X''(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0, \quad (20)$$

$$X'(0) = X'(\pi), \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha))}{T(t; \alpha)} = -\lambda.$$

Let's solve the Sturm-Liouville problem (20) that we obtained using the boundary conditions (21). Since problem (20) is a second-order differential equation with constant coefficients, we examine the different cases of λ from the characteristic equation to find its eigenvalues.

i) $\lambda < 0$,

$$k^2 + \lambda = 0, k^2 = m^2, k = \mp m$$

$$X(x) = Ae^{mx} + Be^{-m} . \quad (22)$$

Eq. (22) is the eigenfunction. When boundary conditions are applied to find the coefficients in the eigenfunction $A = 0, B = 0, X = 0$ is the obvious solution.

ii) $\lambda = 0$,

$$X'' = 0, X' = a_0, X = a_0x + b_0. \quad (23)$$

When the boundary conditions are applied to the eigenfunction, we find $a_0 = 0, b_0 = 0$ is the obvious solution.

iii) $\lambda > 0$,

$$\lambda = m^2 . k^2 + \lambda = 0, k^2 = -m^2, k = \mp mi.$$

$$X(x) = A_n \cos mx + B_n \sin mx.$$

The periodic boundary conditions given in (17) are applied. The eigenvalue is

$$\lambda_k = (2k)^2.$$

There are two linearly independent functions corresponding to this eigenvalue:

$$X = A_n \cos 2kx + B_n \sin 2kx$$

which are the eigenfunctions.

Let's express the eigenvalue λ in the function T :

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t;\alpha))}{T(t;\alpha)} = -\lambda, 0 < \alpha < 1, \lambda > 0 \text{ [29].}$$

$$T_n(t; \alpha) = C_n E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha).$$

Now, combining X_n and T_n , we can write the eigenfunctions in (19).

$$U_n(x, t; \alpha) = (A_n \cos 2kx + B_n \sin 2kx) \cdot C_n \cdot E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha)$$

By superposition the sum of the solutions is also the solution.

$$U(x, t) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [U_{c_k} \cos 2kx + U_{s_k} \sin 2kx] \cdot E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha) \quad (24)$$

By substituting the initial condition given in (18) into expression (24), we obtain

$$U(x, 0) = \varphi(x) = \frac{U_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} U_{c_k} \cos 2kx + U_{s_k} \sin 2kx,$$

$$U_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) dx,$$

$$U_{c_k} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2kx \, dx,$$

$$U_{s_k} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2kx \, dx.$$

When expressed in the solution:

$$U(x, t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \, dx + \left[\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2kx \, dx \right) \cos 2kx + \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2kx \, dx \right) \sin 2kx \right] E_{\alpha,1}(- (2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha).$$

The solution of equation (16)-(18) is obtained.

3.2 Solution of Nonhomogeneous Parabolic Equation with Fourier Method

$$D_t^\alpha(U(x, t; \alpha)) - U_{xx} = f(x, t), \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \pi, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (25)$$

$$U(0, t) = U(\pi, t), \quad U_x(0, t) = U_x(\pi, t), \quad (26)$$

$$U(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad (27)$$

$$U(x, t; \alpha) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} U_{c_n}(t) \cos 2nx + U_{s_n}(t) \sin 2nx. \quad (28)$$

Now, let us look for a solution in the form of Eq. (28), and express Eq. (28) as Eq. (25).

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [D_t^\alpha(U_{c_n}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{c_n}(t)] \cos 2nx + [D_t^\alpha(U_{s_n}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{s_n}(t)] \sin 2nx = f(x, t).$$

The coefficients $U_0(t)$, $U_{c_n}(t)$ and $U_{s_n}(t)$ are obtained using the Fourier transform.

$$D_t^\alpha(U_0(t)) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \, dx = f_0(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U_0(t)) = f_0(t).$$

Integrate both sides over the interval $[0, t]$.

$$U_0(t) - U_0(0) = \int_0^t f_0(\zeta) \, d\zeta,$$

$$U_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \int_0^t f_0(\zeta) \, d\zeta,$$

$$U_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi f(t, \zeta) \, dt \, d\zeta, \quad (29)$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U_{c_n}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{c_n}(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \cos 2nxdx = f_{c_n}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U_{c_n}(t) + (2n)^2 U_{c_n}(t)) = f_{c_n}(t). \quad (30)$$

The problem in Eq. (30) has a homogeneous solution.

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{cn}(t) + (2n)^2 U_{cn}(t)) = 0,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha (U_{cn}(t))}{U_{cn}(t)} = -(2n)^2,$$

$$U_{cn}(t) = C_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha), \quad (31)$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) - (2n)^2 E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) C_n(t)$$

$$+ (2n)^2 C_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{cn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{cn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_n(t)) = f_{cn}(t) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha))^{-1},$$

$$C_n(t) = C_n(0) + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta,$$

$$C_n(t) = \varphi_{cn} + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta. \quad (32)$$

If Eq. (31) is used in Eq. (32), we have

$$U_{cn}(t) = \left[\varphi_{cn} + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha).$$

Similarly, the same operations are done for $U_{sn}(t)$.

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{sn}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{sn}(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \sin 2nx \, dx = f_{sn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{sn}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{sn}(t) = f_{sn}(t), \quad (33)$$

Homogeneous solution is found.

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{sn}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{sn}(t) = 0,$$

$$U_{sn}(t) = S_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha). \quad (34)$$

If Eq. (34) is used in Eq. (33), we have

$$D_t^\alpha (S_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) - (2n)^2 E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) S_n(t)$$

$$+ (2n)^2 S_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{sn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (S_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{sn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (S_n(t)) = f_{sn}(t) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha))^{-1}.$$

Integrate both sides over the interval $[0, t]$.

$$S_n(t) = S_n(0) + \int_0^t f_{sn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta,$$

$$U_{sn}(t) = \left[\varphi_{sn} + \int_0^t f_{sn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha).$$

To determine the coefficients, the boundary condition (26) is applied. The terms ϕ_0 , ϕ_{cn} , and ϕ_{sn} are obtained using the Fourier method.

$$\varphi_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) dx,$$

$$\varphi_{cn} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2nx dx,$$

$$\varphi_{sn} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2nx dx,$$

$$U(x, t) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_0^\infty U_{cn}(t) \cos 2nx + U_{sn}(t) \sin 2nx,$$

$$U(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 + \int_0^t f_0(t) dt \right) + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\left[\varphi_{cn} + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) \right) \cos 2nx + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\left[\varphi_{sn} + \int_0^t f_{sn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) \right) \sin 2nx.$$

The solution is obtained.

4. Solution of Fractional Derivative Semilinear Pseudo-Parabolic Equations with Periodic Boundary Conditions by the Fourier Method

$$D_t^\alpha (U(x, t; \alpha)) - a^2 U_{xx} - \varepsilon U_{txx} = f(x, t), 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (35)$$

$$U(0, t) = U(\pi, t), U_x(0, t) = U_x(\pi, t), 0 \leq x \leq \pi, 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (36)$$

$$U(0, x) = \varphi(x), \quad (37)$$

$$U(x, t; \alpha) = X(x)T(t; \alpha). \quad (38)$$

Let us look for a homogeneous solution in the form of

$$D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha))X - a^2 X''T - \varepsilon X''D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha)) = 0,$$

$$D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha))X = X'' \left(a^2 T + \varepsilon D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha)) \right),$$

$$\frac{X''}{X} = \frac{D_t^\alpha (T)}{a^2 T + \varepsilon D_t^\alpha (T)} = -\lambda,$$

$$X'' + \lambda X = 0, \quad (39)$$

$$X(0) = X(\pi), X'(0) = X'(\pi),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (T) + \lambda a^2 T + \lambda \varepsilon D_t^\alpha (T) = 0,$$

$$D_t^\alpha (T)(1 + \lambda \varepsilon) = -\lambda a^2 T,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha))}{T(t; \alpha)} = -\frac{\lambda a^2}{1 + \lambda \varepsilon}.$$

Eq. (39) is a Sturm–Liouville problem. Let us determine its eigenvalues and eigenfunctions.

$$X'' + \lambda X = 0$$

i) If $\lambda < 0$, the trivial solution is $X = 0$.

ii) $\lambda = 0, X = a_0, T(t; \alpha) = b_0$.

iii) $\lambda > 0$,

$$X = A \cos mx + B \sin mx,$$

$$\lambda = m^2, \lambda_k = (2k)^2, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

There are two eigenfunctions corresponding to this eigenvalue.

$$X_n = A \cos 2kx + B \sin 2kx \quad (40)$$

$$T_n = E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2k)^2 a^2 t^\alpha}{1+(2k)^2 \varepsilon} \right) \quad (41)$$

By substituting Eqs. (40) and (41) into Eq. (38), we obtain

$$U(x, t, \varepsilon) = a_0 b_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (A \cos 2kx + B \sin 2kx) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2 t^\alpha}{1+(2k)^2 \varepsilon} \right). \quad (42)$$

By substituting Eq. (42) into Eq. (35), we obtain

$$U(x, t, \varepsilon) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (U_{c_k}(t) \cos 2kx + U_{s_k}(t) \sin 2kx).$$

By substituting the last solution into the first equation, we obtain

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}(t)) \cos 2kx + D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}(t)) \sin 2kx + (2ka)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} U_{c_k} \cos 2kx + U_{s_k} \sin 2kx + \varepsilon (2k)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}(t)) \cos 2kx + D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}(t)) \sin 2kx,$$

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} ([D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}) + (2ka)^2 (U_{c_k}) + \varepsilon (2k)^2 (U_{c_k})] \cos 2kx) + ([D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}) + (2ka)^2 (U_{s_k}) + \varepsilon (2k)^2 D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k})] \sin 2kx) = f(x, t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{c_k})] \cos 2kx + [(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{s_k})] \sin 2kx = f(x, t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (U_0(t)) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) dx = f_0(t), \quad (43)$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{c_k}) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \cos 2kx dx = f_{c_k}, \quad (44)$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{s_k}) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \sin 2kx dx = f_{s_k}. \quad (45)$$

Let us solve Eq. (43).

$$D_t^\alpha(U_0(t)) = f_0(t),$$

$$U_0(t) = U_0(0) + I^\alpha f(t),$$

$$U_0(t) = U_0(0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$U_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2(U_{c_k}) = f_{c_k}. \quad (46)$$

The homogeneous solution of Eq. (46) is obtained.

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2(U_{c_k}) = 0,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k})}{U_{c_k}} = -\frac{(2a)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2},$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2a)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right). \quad (47)$$

Eq. (46) is substituted for Eq. (47).

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \left[D_t^\alpha \left(C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right) \right] - \left[-\frac{(2a)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right] +$$

$$(2ak)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \left[D_t^\alpha \left(C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right) \right] - (2ak)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) +$$

$$(2ak)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}.$$

Let us find the homogeneous solution of Eq. (44).

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}(t)) + (2ka)^2 U_{c_k}(t) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}) + (2ka)^2 U_{c_k} = 0,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}(t))}{U_{c_k}(t)} = -\frac{(2ka)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2},$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right).$$

Let us write the obtained expression in Eq. (44).

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \left[D_t^\alpha(C_k(t)) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) - \frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right] +$$

$$(2ka)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(C_k(t)) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_k(t)) = f_{c_k} \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1},$$

$$C_k(t) = C_k(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{c_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau,$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right),$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = \left[C_k(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{c_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right).$$

Similarly,

$$U_{s_k}(t) = \left[S_k(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{s_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right).$$

As a result, the general solution is obtained,

$$U(x, t, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\varphi_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \right] + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\varphi_{c_k}(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{c_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \cos 2kx + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\varphi_{s_k}(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{s_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2a)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2a)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \sin 2kx.$$

5. Conclusions

This study successfully applied the Fourier method to solve homogeneous and non-homogeneous parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions. Eigenvalues and eigenfunctions were obtained via the Sturm–Liouville problem, and Caputo fractional derivatives were used to extend the analysis to fractional-order equations. The analytical solutions were expressed using Gamma, Beta, and Mittag–Leffler functions. The results confirm that the Fourier method is an effective tool for solving classical and fractional semilinear pseudo-parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions.

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